

SHAYTAN: A CLEAR ENEMY

Ibn Kathir in his tafsir states, “Iblis, the enemy of Allah, envied Adam because Allah honoured Adam. He said, ‘I was created from fire, and he was created from clay.’ Therefore, the first error ever committed was arrogance, for the enemy of Allah was too arrogant to prostrate before Adam.”

Further, it has been recorded in the Sahih,

“No person who has the weight of a mustard seed of arrogance in his heart shall enter Paradise.”¹

Iblis had disbelief, arrogance, and rebellion, all of which caused him to be expelled from the holy presence of Allah, and His mercy.

Allah says,

“Did I not enjoin upon you, O children of Adam, that you not worship Satan - [for] indeed, he is to you a clear enemy - And that you worship [only] Me? This is a straight path.”²

The kufr of arrogance and pride was the kufr of Shaytan because he did not deny or reject the command of Allah, but he met it with pride and arrogance. From this arose the kufr of those who knew and believed that Allah’s Messenger ﷺ had come with the truth from Allah but did not acknowledge it out of pride and arrogance. The mufasssireen say this was the kufr of the Jews,

“...then when there came to them that which they had recognized, they disbelieved in it.”³

Iblis was expelled from Paradise over pride. A proud person considers himself self-sufficient and not in need of Allah. Kibr (pride) builds one’s ego and this is a bad trait which is detestable to Allah.

Allah says in a hadith qudsi,

“Pride is my cloak, and glory is my wrap, so he who competes Me in either of these, I will cast him into the Fire.”⁴

Every action has a time and a place in which it occurs and we, as humans, do not possess either. Mankind does not have the power to maintain his own or any other’s life. So how can any man or any creation take pride in anything? There is only One Absolute; that is Allah:

“He is Allah, other than whom there is no deity, the Sovereign, the Pure, the Perfection, the Bestower of Faith, the Overseer, the Exalted in Might, the Compeller, the Superior...”⁵

Hence, pride, which is in fact self-praise, is forbidden for the servants (abeed) of Allah.

The Messenger of Allah ﷺ said,

“Indeed, Allah revealed to me, humble yourselves until none is proud over another and none is oppressive over another.”⁶

In the tafsir of Ibn Kathir, the following is related:

“The Jews used to invoke Allah to send a prophet so that they would gain victory over the Arab disbelievers. But when Allah sent Muhammad ﷺ and they saw that

he was not one of them, they rejected him and envied the Arabs, even though they knew that he was the Messenger of Allah ﷺ. Hence, Allah said,

‘Then when there came to them that which they had recognized, they disbelieved in it. So let the curse of Allah be on the disbelievers.’⁷

Shaytan hates mankind, the children of Adam. He is hostile towards them because he is cursed and has been banished from the Mercy of Allah due to his refusal to prostrate to their father, Adam.

‘For he had said, 'I will surely take from among Your servants a specific portion. And I will mislead them...'⁸

Iblis already knows that his destination is the Fire and he is eager to mislead and corrupt mankind, so as to increase the number of his followers to share his fate. He hopes to take everyone with him to Hell; out of envy, hatred, kufr and stubbornness.

‘Indeed, Satan is an enemy to you; so take him as an enemy. He only invites his party to be among the companions of the Blaze.’⁹

Shaytan is a deceiver, a corrupter. Thus, Shaytan cannot do more than call people to misguidance and make it look attractive to them. He has no actual power over them to force them into doing what he wants. People who respond to his call do so because it suits their whims and desires. Hence, the blame is attached to only those who respond to him. On the Day of Judgment, the qareen¹⁰ will testify against man and disown his actions, saying that he, himself, was misguided. He will claim that the man was receptive to the falsehood and resistant to the truth. Allah says,

‘His [devil] companion will say, 'Our Lord, I did not make him transgress, but he [himself] was in extreme error.' [Allah] will say, 'Do not dispute before Me, while I had already presented to you the warning.’¹¹

The Pact

‘And [mention] when your Lord took from the children of Adam - from their loins -

their descendants and made them testify of themselves, [saying to them], ‘Am I not your Lord?’ They said, ‘Yes, we have testified.’ [This] - lest you should say on the day of Resurrection, ‘Indeed, we were of this unaware.’¹²

A proud person considers himself self-sufficient and not in need of Allah.

This surah is a reminder of the primordial pact, which Allah made with all human beings prior to their entrance into this world. Thus, “to not worship Shaytan” means, “to not obey Shaytan”

because the obedience of others in areas prohibited by Allah is a form of ibadah. Ali ibn Abi Talib relates the following hadith in the sahihayn, where the Messenger of Allah ﷺ said:

‘No obedience is due to anyone if it involves disobedience to Allah. Indeed obedience is in what is good.’¹³

One can also not legalize the unlawful and declare the unlawful to be the lawful as a result of ijihad. However, if done with sincerity in which he was striving to follow in the footsteps of Allah’s prophets and messengers, but he failed, he will not be held responsible for his mistake. According to the Messenger of Allah ﷺ, he might achieve the reward for his efforts at ijihad based on the hadith of Amr ibn al-Aas, who related that he heard the Messenger of Allah ﷺ say,

‘If a ruler makes a ruling striving [to find what is correct] and is correct, he gets two rewards. But if he rules striving [to find what is correct] and is mistaken, he gets one reward.’¹⁴

However, if a person knew that monks or rabbis were mistaken and despite this followed them and rejected the statements of the prophets and messengers of Allah, he would have fallen into this type of shirk and the rejection of Allah. Moreover, he will receive his due share of punishment if he supports this mistake with his strength and power while knowing that it is wrong. This form of shirk and the one who commits it, deserve the penalty and punishment.

The Prophet ﷺ said,

‘Shaytan lies waiting for a person in all his

paths. In the path of Islam, he will tell him, ‘Will you become a Muslim and leave the religion of your fathers and grandfathers?’ If the person disobeys him, and becomes a Muslim, he will meet him on the path of hijrah. He will tell him, ‘Will you leave your land and your sky? It is not wise.’ If the person does not submit and continues on his way, Shaytan will wait for him on the road to striving in the path of Allah, saying, ‘Will you go to struggle putting yourself and your wealth at risk? You will fight and be killed. Your wife will find another partner, your money will be divided,’ (and in another version, ‘and your children will be orphans’). If the person disobeys Shaytan, and is killed, Allah will owe him the right to enter Paradise.” [Musnad Ahmad]

¹Sahih Muslim, Book 1, Hadith Number 16

²Quran 36:60-61

³Quran 2:89

⁴Sunan Abu Dawud, Book 33, Hadith Number 4079

⁵Quran 59:23

⁶Sahih Muslim, Book 1, Hadith Number 602

⁷Ibn Kathir, Tafseer Ibn Kathir for Quran 2:89

⁸Quran 4: 118-119

⁹Quran 35:6

¹⁰Our jinn companion who encourages us to do evil deeds.

¹¹Quran 50:27-28

¹²Quran 7:172

¹³Sahih Muslim, Book 91, Hadith Number 363

¹⁴Sunan an-Nasa’i, Book 49, Hadith 5383

References:

1. Dr. B. Philips, (2005), Tafsir Soorah Yaseen, IOU publication
2. Al Quran Kareem, translation by Mufti Taqi Usmani, available at [<http://www.central-mosque.com/>]
3. Ibn Kathir (2000), Tafsir Ibn Kathir, abridged, Darussalam Publishers, Riyadh, Saudia Arabia
4. Selections from Hadith in electronic format from Musnad of Ahmad, Sahih Bukhari, and Sahih Muslim

